

ARIES

Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 730871

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Set-up of the Proof-of-Concept innovation-funding scheme

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ABSTRACT

The ARIES Proof of Concept (PoC) innovation fund is intended to provide financial support to projects at their very early stage or pre-seed stage with the scope of turning research outputs into a proposition that has impact, innovation and technology transfer potential. This deliverable reports the setting up of the procedures, the criteria, the method, used for the management of the PoC, and the timeline of its implementation.

ARIES Consortium, 2018

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For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The ARIES Proof of Concept (PoC) innovation fund is intended to provide financial support to projects at their very early stage or pre-seed stage with the scope of turning research outputs into a proposition that has impact, innovation and technology transfer potential. This deliverable reports the setting up of the procedures, the criteria, the method, used for the management of the PoC, and the timeline of its implementation.

1. Introduction

Among the strategic goals of ARIES is enhancing innovation in the accelerator community and developing novel concepts and technologies in the related technology sectors. This will be done by involving industry in the setting up of co-innovation programmes and in the selection and promotion of innovative technologies, while supporting the societal application of accelerators.

As one of the ways to implement the ARIES strategic platform, is the Proof-of-Concept (PoC) fund that within the activities of WP14, offers financial support to study, develop and establish the commercial feasibility of novel concepts within accelerator science.

In this document we will describe in detail what the PoC is, its aims and the prospected destination of the fund. We will then report the eligibility criteria for participation, and the process of selection, evaluation, awards of projects that have been defined in collaboration with the ARIES Steering Committee and Industry Advisory Board. Finally, we will relate the present status of project selection (April 2018).

2. Proof of Concept fund : Overview

The ARIES Proof-of-Concept (PoC) fund offers financial support to study, develop and establish the commercial feasibility of novel concepts within accelerator science.

Its aims are:

- To increase the level of innovation and technology transfer from accelerator science.
- To increase the impact of research, concepts & technology arising from the ARIES project.
- To minimise the risks associated with innovation for small-medium enterprises (SMEs).

In order to be eligible for funding, lead applicants must be part of the ARIES consortium (i.e.: beneficiaries or partner organisations). However, additional participants are not required to be connected with ARIES. The work proposed must demonstrate the potential for the development of technologies and expertise.

The funding can be exclusively used for:

- Undertaking further scientific and technical development of an idea,
- Improving an intellectual property (IP) position, such as supporting further works to exemplify or broaden patent claims
- Gaining further information about the market for new products or processes.
- Identifying potential licences of opportunities for joint ventures.

The PoC fund cannot be used for funding “blue sky” research, to sustain the patent cost, or to purchase large equipment and materials.

The overall amount foreseen in the project proposal for the Proof-of-Concept Fund is 210,000 EUR, intended to support between two and four projects.

3. Method and Procedures

A procedure for identification, selection and award of projects to be funded by Proof-of-Concept fund has been finalized as scope of work in Task 14.2 of WP14. The ARIES Steering Committee at its second meeting in September 2017, has approved the package of documents presented by the WP14 leader that are meant to manage the implementation of the PoC, including the methodology of projects selection. The document package has been amended according to requests of Project Coordinator, WP14 task leaders and other ARIES project beneficiaries.

After the approval of STC#2 the document has been made public within the community and an ARIES PoC navigation web site prepared <http://aries.web.cern.ch/content/aries-proof-concept-fund>. The web site has been made public in November 2017, according to a well-defined communication strategy and to the timeline of the project.

It is important to notice that the web site mentioned above includes not only the Procedure of Evaluation, but the full package of approved documentation, including guidelines and templates to inform, help and support potential proponents of projects.

In particular, at the website, it is possible to download the following documents:

- **Proposal Guidelines**, whose purpose is to provide proposal guidelines for potential applicants regarding application to the ARIES Proof-of-Concept fund.
http://aries.web.cern.ch/sites/aries.web.cern.ch/files/download/ARIES_POC_Proposal_Guidelines_nov2017.pdf
- **Evaluation Methodology**, whose purpose is to provide information to potential applicants regarding the evaluation and selection procedure for the ARIES Proof-of-Concept fund
http://aries.web.cern.ch/sites/aries.web.cern.ch/files/download/ARIES_POC_Evaluation_Methodology_Nov2017.pdf
- **PoC Proposal Template**, whose purpose is to provide guidance for the preparation of the proposals, according to the necessary requirements of formats, length of the documents, mandatory content of the document,
http://aries.web.cern.ch/sites/aries.web.cern.ch/files/download/ARIES_POC_Proposal_Template_V5.docx
- **PoC poster** (for dissemination and communication scope).

The finalized implementation procedure is aimed at fulfilling the principles of transparency and equality. Indeed, it is foreseen that through a public “advertised” call for PoC, with fixed deadline, projects are presented for selection and evaluated by an Evaluation Committee (EvCo) which is appointed by the Industrial Advisory Board IAB of ARIES. The EvCo can be supported by appointed ad-hoc selected experts, according to specific needs.

Selection criterias of projects eligible for PoC funding, account for:

1. Impact → the capability to drive a shift in a scientific paradigm. Impact is the market value of an idea.
2. Novelty → the capability to drive an incremental, disruptive, or process –product innovation (added value).

3. Application → the capability to demonstrate (via business plans) that the market is ready, or willing, to take up the innovation (market pull) and the transfer to industry is feasible (partnership with industry).

CALL FOR PROPOSALS

The ARIES Proof-of-Concept fund offers support to early-stage research to develop or study the commercial feasibility of novel concepts within accelerator science. Projects should aim to:

- Develop an idea
- Improve intellectual property position
- Gain market information on new product/concept

Who can apply?
Lead applicants must be part of the ARIES Consortium (beneficiaries or partner organisations).
Additional participants are not required to be connected to ARIES.

Timeline
Call opens: December 1st 2017
Deadline: 31st March 2018

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For information on how to apply, please visit: <https://aries.web.cern.ch/poc>

Figure 1: ARIES PoC poster

4. How to apply

All the steps to apply a project for PoC funding can be undertaken directly at the public web address, where application templates are available and as well a Submission Form to be filled up <http://aries.web.cern.ch/content/call-proposals>

In this way it is possible to trace and record the exact timing of the applications, respecting the principle of transparency.

5. Timeline

According to the ARIES Description-of-work, the implementation of the PoC should have started after M12 (April 2018). However, having completed the setting-up of the process and received the approval from the Steering Committee already at the end of 2017, it was decided by the ARIES management not to wait and to start the PoC implementation in advance of the original deadline.

Following this decision, the web site was made public at the end of November 2017. The PoC has been advertised within the ARIES community by mailings, at all meetings of ARIES Committees and Work Packages, and at all Workshops organized between November 2017 and March 2018. For example, the PoC was largely advertised at the ARIES co-innovation Workshop with industry at Brussels on 07/02/2018. The Call for Proposal has been opened to applications on December 1, 2017 and deadline for applications was end of March 2018.

The Industry Advisory Board (IAB) has been appointed by the ARIES Governing Board (GB) by mailing vote at the end of November 2017. Initial meetings and teleconferences among members of the IAB have been organized between that moment and March 2018. The meetings of IAB resulted in the appointing of the EvCo in March 2018. This will provide possibility to start the activities of evaluating the eligible projects presented, and eventually, to prepare the GB decision for awarding of funds before the summer 2018.

For an update status of the PoC fund implementation, and for a timeline to the award of the funding, please refer to the Annex 1.

6. Conclusion

The ARIES project has successfully set-up the complete procedure for the management of the Proof-of-Concept fund, including the method of evaluation and the criteria of selection of projects. The timeline of implementation has been integrated into the project work plan, and the definition and activation of the proper communication channel have been adopted.

7. Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ARIES	Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
IAB	Industrial Advisory Board
PoC	Proof of Concept
STC	Steering Committee
GB	Governing Board

8. Annex 1

The implementation of PoC has started with the closing of the Call for Proposals, on 31 March, 2018. At the closing time, 10 proposals had been submitted, of which one out of the imposed time deadline.

The title of the proposal submitted with the leading institution is:

1. Field Confined Radiofrequency Ion Source for Medical and Industrial Applications (CIEMAT)
2. Fast closing UHV all-metal gate valve for use in particle accelerator systems (GSI)
3. Atomic Layer Deposition: an innovative approach for next generation particle accelerators (CEA)
4. Accelerator Diagnostics using Innovative Adaptive Optics (InnoAdo) (University of Liverpool)
5. Compact Hybrid Quadrupole for Diffraction Limited Storage Ring (SOLEIL)
6. Investigation of new methods for the manufacturing of Copper-Diamond Composites with tailored thermo-physical properties (RHP)
7. SRF Surfacing (CEA)

8. Eliminating the spread of antibiotics resistance thorough (University of Huddersfield)
9. Development of hybrid electron accelerator system for the treatment of marine diesel exhaust gases (Riga Technical University)

The evaluation and award timeline is:

1. Opening of the proposals, and start of the Evaluation Process: April 4, 2018
2. End of the Remote Evaluation Process: April 30, 2018 (latest)
3. Consolidation of the Individual Evaluations: May 7, 2018 (latest)
4. Evaluation Report drafting and Teleconference → May 31, 2018 (latest)
5. Notification of the first 4 scored Proposals and presentation of proposals at CERN: June 15, 2018
6. Recommendation to Steering Committee for award of funding: 29 Jun, 2018.

The composition of the Evaluation Committee is:

- | | |
|----------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| 1. John Allen | Elekta |
| 2. Jean Luc Lancelot | Sigmaphi |
| 3. Francesco Estrafallaces | CNI |
| 4. Francis Martin | International Irradiation Association |
| 5. Julio Lucas | Elytt |
| 6. Tomas Eriksson | GE Healthcare |
| 7. Hanspeter Vogel | Research Instruments |